

EFFECT OF PLY THICKNESS ON MECHANICAL PROPERTY OF CFRP SYMMETRIC ANGLE-PLY LAMINATES

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1 Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have been used for aerospace structures because of its high stiffness and strength, and low density. This paper deals with mechanical property and damage evolution in CFRP symmetric angle-ply laminates with different ply thickness. Specifically, we evaluate damage evolution of thick ply thickness laminates and thin ply thickness laminates through the use of damage model which focuses on mesoscale. It is important for efficient design of composite structures to examine effect of ply thickness on mechanical properties of CFRP laminates. To investigate damage evolution in CFRP symmetric angle-ply laminates, we use mesoscale damage model proposed by Ladeveze et al [1]. They proposed damage model which applied continuum damage model to composites, and predicted mechanical properties of composites. Herakovich et al [2] predicted mechanical properties and evaluated damage evolution of $[(\pm 45)_3]_s$ laminates that exhibit large deformation by use of the damage model which takes into account fiber rotation and reduction in cross sectional area.

2 Experimental program

In this study, T700/2500 (Toray Co., Ltd.) composite has been investigated. Four different laminates $[(\pm 45)_{12}]_s$, $[(\pm 67.5)_{12}]_s$ which use 48 plies of thin 0.05mm thick prepregs and $[(\pm 45)_4]_s$, $[(\pm 67.5)_4]_s$ which use 16 plies of normal 0.15mm thick prepregs has been investigated. It should be noted that the laminate thickness is almost the same, but the ply thickness are quite different. In 48-ply specimen each +45 and -45 ply thickness is 0.05mm. On the other hand, in 16-ply specimen, if we regard the blocked $(+45)_4$ or $(-45)_4$ plies as one 45 or -45 ply, the thickness of blocked plies are 0.6mm. The one ply thickness in 48-ply specimen is

12 times thinner than that in 16-ply specimen. Specimen length was 260mm, width was 20mm and thickness was 2.4mm. GFRP tabs were bonded to the ends for the load introduction. Biaxial Strain gauges were bonded at the center of the specimen. Uniaxial high-elongation strain gages were only used to $[(\pm 45)_{12}]_s$ laminates. We performed tensile tests and cyclic loading-unloading tests at the crosshead speed 1.0 mm/min.

3 Experimental results

3.1 Monotonic tensile test

We carried out monotonic tensile test to investigate stress-strain relationship. Fig. 1 shows stress-strain behavior in $[(+45)_4/(-45)_4]_s$ and $[(\pm 45)_{12}]_s$ laminates. Fig. 2 shows stress-strain behavior in $[(+67.5)_4/(-67.5)_4]_s$ and $[(\pm 67.5)_{12}]_s$ laminates. Table 1 shows mechanical properties of each laminate in monotonic tensile tests. It is clear that $[(\pm 45)_{12}]_s$ laminate exhibits larger failure strain and higher strength than $[(+45)_4/(-45)_4]_s$ laminates. $[(+67.5)_4/(-67.5)_4]_s$ and $[(\pm 67.5)_{12}]_s$ laminates show the similar tendency of $[(+45)_4/(-45)_4]_s$ and $[(\pm 45)_{12}]_s$ laminates. Thin ply thickness specimen (48-ply specimen) indicated higher strength and higher fracture strain than thick ply thickness specimen (16-ply specimen).

Since strength and fracture strain indicate different tendency, we carried out cyclic loading-unloading test to estimate damage evolution due to ply thickness.

3.2 Loading-Unloading test

In this study, we evaluated damage evolution by testing loading-unloading test. The loading-unloading cycle were repeated five or six times. Damage is characterized by material stiffness loss. Therefore, as the elastic modulus loss of each cycle

to the undamaged elastic modulus, damage variable is written as:

$$d = 1 - \frac{E}{E_0} \quad (1)$$

where, d is damage variable, E is elastic modulus at each cycle, E_0 is undamaged elastic modulus. Elastic modulus of each cycle is determined as gradient between intersection point of loading process and unloading process and point which loading process change.

4 Mesoscale damage model

We can know damage evolution by using mesoscale damage model with results of tensile tests of each laminate. In this study, we used mesoscale damage model proposed by Ladevese et al [1]. Mesoscale damage model focus on intermediate scale between micro and macro scale. It does not consider identification of the specific damage at the microscopic level, such as fiber-matrix debonding or matrix cracking. This model assume that damage is generated uniformly through the thickness of a layer. We assume an individual layer of a plane stress state.

4.1 Damage kinematics

The strain energy for an individual layer of laminate in a state of plane stress is written:

$$E_D = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\sigma_{11}^2}{E_{11}^o} + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{G_{12}^o(1-d_{12})} + \frac{\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_+^2}{E_{22}^o(1-d_{22})} + \frac{\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_-^2}{E_{22}^o} - \frac{2\nu_{12}^o}{E_{11}^o} \sigma_{11} \sigma_{22} \right] \quad (2)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \langle a \rangle_+ &= a \quad \text{if } a \geq 0; \quad \text{otherwise } \langle a \rangle_+ = 0 \\ \langle a \rangle_- &= a \quad \text{if } a \leq 0; \quad \text{otherwise } \langle a \rangle_- = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

d_{12} and d_{22} are scalar damage variables, that represent loss of the shear modulus and the transverse Young's modulus, respectively. Subscript 1 describes fiber direction and subscript 2 does transverse direction. These two variables are given by loading-unloading test results. The superscript 0 indicates undamaged value. We assume no stiffness loss in fiber direction, because fiber

break doesn't occur. From eq. (2), we can determine thermodynamic forces Y_{12} and Y_{22} in terms of stress components and damage variables. They are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{12} &= \frac{\partial E_D}{\partial d_{12}} \Big|_{\sigma} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{G_{12}^o(1-d_{12})^2} \\ Y_{22} &= \frac{\partial E_D}{\partial d_{22}} \Big|_{\sigma} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sigma_{22}^2}{G_{22}^o(1-d_{22})^2} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Two variables Y_{12} and Y_{22} correspond to the energy release rate. They govern the damage evolution. Damage development is described by using these variables as:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{Y}(t) &= \sup_{\tau \leq t} (\sqrt{Y_{12}(\tau)} + bY_{22}(\tau)) \\ \underline{Y}'(t) &= \sup_{\tau \leq t} (\sqrt{Y_{22}(\tau)}) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where b is a material constant coupling between transverse tension and shear effects. These two variables of thermodynamic forces, $\underline{Y}(t)$ and $\underline{Y}'(t)$, that are associated with damage variables.

4.2 Shear damage evolution

From the loading-unloading tests on the $[(+45)_4/(-45)_4]_s$ and $[(\pm 45)_{12}]_s$ laminates, we can determine σ_{12} - ε_{12} shear behavior and shear damage evolution. Shear and transverse stress are given by classical lamination theory in terms of applied axial stress σ_{xx} as:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{22} &\approx 0 \\ \sigma_{12} &= 0.5\sigma_{xx} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

and, shear and transverse strain are given in terms of measured longitudinal and transverse strain, ε_{xx} and ε_{yy} as:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{22} &\approx 0 \\ \varepsilon_{12} &= 0.5(\varepsilon_{xx} - \varepsilon_{yy}) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The result of cyclic loading-unloading tensile test of $[(\pm 45)_{12}]_s$ laminate is shown in Fig. 3.

We consider that shear force dominate in ± 45 laminates. Thermodynamic force associated with damage variables are written as:

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{22} &= 0 \\ \underline{Y} &= \max_{\tau \leq t} (Y_{12}) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 4 shows shear damage evolution relationship between shear damage variables d_{12} and thermodynamic force \underline{Y} given by eq. (8). Damage developed linearly at the early stages on both specimen 48-ply laminates and 16-ply laminates. In 48-ply laminates, d_{12} became almost constant although the stress increases. It is necessary to investigate damage state microscopically at each loading condition. Consideration of fiber rotation change fiber orientation due to tensile loading is also required in damage model.

4.3 Transverse damage evolution

Damage development in transverse direction can be determined from cyclic tensile tests of $[(\pm 67.5)_{12}]_s$ and $[(+67.5)_4/(-67.5)_4]_s$ laminates. Stresses of $[\pm\theta]_s$ laminates under tensile loading are determined by following equations :

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{11} &= B\sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{22} &= (1-B)\sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{12} &= \frac{-1}{2mn} [B(1-2m^2) + m^2] \sigma_{xx}\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

where, σ_{xx} represents applied stress. B depends on elastic properties and ply orientation, using $n=\sin\theta$ and $m=\cos\theta$,

$$B = \left[\frac{m^2(2m^2 - 1 + 4m^2n^2) \frac{G_{12}}{E_{22}}}{4m^2n^2 \frac{G_{12}}{E_{22}} + (2m^2 - 1)(m^2 - n^2)} \right] \quad (10)$$

When θ is 67.5° , eq. (9) gives $B=0.218$ in the elastic region. It is assumed that B is constant parameter throughout loading history. Then we can determine stress-strain relationships of transverse direction. Fig. 5 shows transverse behavior. From equation (4) and (5) using experimental results, we can determine transverse damage behavior of transverse damage parameter d_{22} and the variable \underline{Y} . Fig. 6 shows transverse damage behavior in $[(\pm 67.5)_{12}]_s$ and $[(+67.5)_4/(-67.5)_4]_s$ laminates. It is clear that thin 48ply specimen is excellent at resistance of damage.

5 Conclusion

We carried out monotonic tensile tests and loading-unloading tests on $[(+45)_4/(-45)_4]_s$ (16-ply), $[(\pm 45)_{12}]_s$ (48-ply), $[(+67.5)_4/(-67.5)_4]_s$ (16-ply), $[(\pm 67.5)_{12}]_s$ (48-ply) laminates, of T700/2500 (Toray Co., Ltd.) composites. We investigated effect of ply thickness on mechanical property and damage evolution. In $\pm 45^\circ$ angle-ply laminates, shear

damage evolution was measured. In $\pm 67.5^\circ$ angle-ply laminates, transverse damage evolution was measured. It has been shown that thin ply thickness laminates (48-ply) are superior in terms of resistance to damage, such as damage initiation, in comparison to thick (blocked) ply laminates (16-ply). In $\pm 67.5^\circ$ angle-ply laminates, it have a small effect of ply thickness in comparison to $\pm 45^\circ$ angle-ply laminates. For the future, we need to investigate different orientation angle-ply laminates such as $\pm 30^\circ$ angle-ply laminates.

Fig. 1 Stress-Strain curves of $[(+45)_4/(-45)_4]_s$ and $[(\pm 45)_{12}]_s$ laminates in monotonic tensile test.

Fig. 2 Stress-Strain curves of $[(+67.5)_4/(-67.5)_4]_s$ and $[(\pm 67.5)_{12}]_s$ laminates in monotonic tensile test.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of each laminate

	$[(\pm 45)_{12}]_s$	$[(+45)_4/(-45)_4]_s$	$[(\pm 67.5)_{12}]_s$	$[(+67.5)_4/(-67.5)_4]_s$
Young's modulus (GPa)	16.7	14.4	10.6	9.2
Tensile Strength (Mpa)	261.5	116.1	87.6	47.9
Longitudinal strain at fracture(%)	14.1	1.91	0.96	0.53
Poisson's ratio	0.78	0.77	0.19	0.17

Fig. 3 Shear behavior of $[(\pm 45)_{12}]_s$ laminate in loading-unloading tensile tests.

Fig. 4 Shear damage evolution of $[(+45)_4/(-45)_4]_s$ and $[(\pm 45)_{12}]_s$ laminates.

Fig. 5 Transverse behavior of $[(\pm 67.5)_{12}]_s$ laminate in loading-unloading tensile tests.

Fig. 6 Transverse damage evolution of $[(+67.5)_4/(-67.5)_4]_s$ and $[(\pm 67.5)_{12}]_s$ laminates .

References

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